

Personal Data Management

Data Masking

In research, personal data have to be anonymized or pseudonymized as soon as the processing purpose permits. Personal data may only be processed with the informed consent of the person concerned. This guide explains the basic terms.

Definitions

Pseudonymization refers to the removal of personal references, whereby a mapping key (i.e., a table that translates pseudonym, e.g. study identifier (ID), to person) is retained for the re-personalization of the information. If data is pseudonymized, the conditions under which a person may be identified and how the mapping key is stored must be regulated (key management). Unlike anonymized data, pseudonymized data remain personal data.

Anonymization means that the reference to a person is irreversibly (= definitively) removed in such a way that it is no longer possible to identify the individual without disproportionate effort. Anonymized data are no longer regarded as personal data.

Encryption is a method of protecting data from unauthorized access. It means that a plain text is converted (encoded) into a non-interpretable character string (ciphertext) by means of an encryption procedure. One or more keys (= codes) are used as crucial parameters for encryption. Secure encryption makes it practically impossible to retrieve the plain text without the appropriate key. However, secure encryption must be done correctly. When in doubt, contact your IT.

Useful data anonymization tools

- [ARX](#)
- [Argus](#)
- [scdMicro](#)
- [QualiAnon](#)

Data Masking Example

Collected data

ID	Name	Date of birth	Disease	Treatment
DS001	Alan Smith	01.06.2001	Appendicitis	Operation

The original data contains personal data (in this case: name, date of birth, disease and treatment) and is assigned a study ID.

Pseudonymized data

ID	Name	Date of birth	Disease	Treatment
DS001			Appendicitis	Operation

Mapping Key

ID	Name	Date of birth	Disease	Treatment
DS001	Alan Smith	01.06.2001		

Pseudonymized data refer to datasets in which direct identifiers (in this case: name and date of birth) are replaced with a unique pseudonym (ID). The mapping key – required to re-identify the data subject – is stored separately from the research dataset. While pseudonymization reduces the risk of direct identification, re-identification remains possible if the mapping key is accessed and linked to the pseudonymized data.

Anonymized data

ID	Name	Date of birth	Disease	Treatment
DS001			Appendicitis	Operation

The mapping key is deleted, which means that it is no longer possible to link the ID in the research table to the personal data originally associated with that ID.

Encrypted data

ID	Name	Date of birth	Disease	Treatment
ZTUVqwEAb Uf+M0tKeQX zQVjnl3VMM vJTdpgB9eIM bzs	xu05js8QCrn 90lj1uaflSzUy bf8uMEvrDT+ KSXvJY24	lYtVtyocsRqT l6QANxqfDc jxxvRHSWEG jQY54ddSvzE	TOP2AMUh /Fgs2XhoCY 2Zv30qaKP wZ/4A7t1Fp LcRBng	P7Hz796XwSk PXeQvGv2PG cR8XUmG/IC0 kSkv6n/bnlc

Encrypted data have been converted from its original, readable form into an unreadable, encoded format through cryptographic algorithms. Access to the original information is restricted to authorized parties in possession of the appropriate decryption key.

